

was 161 cm at An Giang and 146 cm at Hau Giang in late Oct (see figure).

At An Giang, Nang Tay Dum yielded highest (3.6 t/ha) and was significantly superior to Nang Tay Lon and Sa Mo Chum. It also had the highest number of filled panicles. Nang Tay Lon had highest grain weight and Sa Mo Chum had more panicles/m². Ba Bong was superior at Hau Giang. Soil type may have caused differences in varietal performance in the two locations. Hau Giang has slightly acid sulfate soil and An Giang has normal alluvial soil.

Introduced varieties had a higher percentage of unfilled grains than local varieties, except Pin Gaew 56, which had a large number of filled grains/panicle and high grain weight (see table).

BKNFR76031-1-1-13-1, BKNFR76047-4-3-1, and RD19 had less adaptability in An Giang, a typical floating rice area, because they have lower elongation ability and can be damaged by deep flooding.

Leb Mue Nahng 111 and Pin Gaew 56 had elongation ability similar to that of local varieties. Ba Bong and Pin Gaew 56 were

late maturing and had longer plants and good kneeing ability, making them suitable for deep water.

Elongation rate of some deepwater rices of Bihar, India

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Deepwater rices are characterized by rapid elongation of stem, sheath, and leaf blade when water rises. If water rises gradually, they keep their leaves above the surface. Elongation rate of many local deepwater cultivars grown in Bihar has not been established. We recorded daily elongation of local varieties Janaki (64-117), BR14, Pichar, Barogar, Desaria,

Malida, and 62-68.

Forty-day-old potted seedlings were submerged in a 1-m-deep water tank. Water level was adjusted daily, and height was measured on 4 consecutive days.

Daily elongation rate varied. Maximum daily elongation was 26 cm for Desaria, 25 cm for Barogar, 18 cm for Pichar, 13 cm for Janaki (64-117), 12 cm for BR14 and for 62-68, and 7 cm for Malida. The time of greatest elongation also varied. Desaria, Barogar, and 62-68 had greatest elongation on day 1; Pichar, Malida, and BR14 on day 4; and Janaki (64-117) on day 3 (see table).

Barogar and Desaria, both floating rices, elongated fastest, and had greatest day 1 elongation, which is desirable.

Average daily elongation of local deepwater rice in Bihar, India.

Variety	Av daily elongation (cm)							
	Day 1		Day 2		Day 3		Day 4	
	Av	Range	Av	Range	Av	Range	Av	Range
Janaki (64-117)	2	0.2-5.4	5	0.7-6.5	5	1.0-12.7	3	0.5-10.8
Pichar	4	1.2-8.2	2	0.3-3.8	4	0.5-13.3	14	1.5-18.0
Barogar	16	8.0-25.0	8	4.0-17.0	8	2.0-17.0	8	2.0-17.2
Desaria	9	2.0-14.0	6	1.4-10.4	14	5.1-26.1	5	1.0-13.0
Malida	1	0.2-3.5	3	1.6-5.0	3	1.0-4.5	6	3.0-7.0
62-68	7	4.5-10.0	8	5.5-12.0	4	1.0-6.2	2	0.5-6.1
BR14	7	0.5-7.0	5	0.5-10.0	4	0.5-10.3	9	5.0-11.7

Field Problems of Tropical Rice

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